

This is a preprint of an article published in:

Antonio J. Gómez-Núñez, Benjamín Vargas-Quesada, Félix de Moya-Anegón (2016). Updating the SCImago journal and country rank classification: A new approach using Ward's clustering and alternative combination of citation measures. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 67(1):178-190. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/asi.23370>

**UPDATING SCIMAGO JOURNAL & COUNTRY RANK CLASSIFICATION: A
NEW APPROACH FROM WARD'S CLUSTERING AND ALTERNATIVE
COMBINATION OF CITATION MEASURES**

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Abstract

This study introduces a new proposal to refine classification of Scimago Journal & Country Rank (SJR) platform by using clustering techniques and an alternative combination of citation measures from an initial 18,891 SJR journal network. Thus, a journal-journal matrix including fractionalized values of direct citation, co-citation and coupling at once was symmetrized by *cosine similarity* and later transformed into distances before performing clustering.

The results provided a new cluster-based subject structure comprising 290 clusters which emerge from executing Ward's clustering in two phases and a mixed labeling procedure based on *tf-idf* scores of original SJR category tags and significant words extracted from journal titles. A total of 13,716 SJR journals were classified through this new cluster-based scheme generated.

Although over 5,000 journals were omitted in the classification process, the method produced a consistent classification with a balanced structure of coherent and well-defined clusters, a moderated multi-assignment of journals and a softer concentration of journals over clusters than in SJR original categories. New subject disciplines as 'Nanoscience & Nanotechnology' or 'Social Work' were also detected evidencing a good performance of our approach both by refining journal classification and updating the subject classification structure.

Keywords

Journal classification ; Scimago Journal & Country Rank ; Ward hierarchical clustering ; Citation-based networks ; Bibliometrics

Introduction

Classification schemes for bibliometric application increased in the wake of the remarkable growth and development of scientific disciplines and research topics. This issue is closely related to the proliferation of scientific information described by Price (1963) in his book entitled *Little Science, Big Science*. According to Yagi, Badash, and Beaver (1996) Price's interest in measuring the growth of science was fostered by the emergence of the first large multidisciplinary citation database, namely, the Science Citation Index (SCI) at the beginning of 1960s. Since then, databases started to arise as the main service for recording bibliographic data of scholarly literature mainly published in scientific journal articles, conference proceedings, books, etc.

However, all information covered by databases has to be maintained and organized in an adequate way in order to facilitate tasks linked to information seeking and retrieval, but also to assist information specialists in quantifying various aspects arising from the analysis of science systems and research performance. Bibliometric studies devoted to these issues have helped science professionals in making decisions on funding, in science policy and research management. In order to be able to offer consistent and reliable results, correct delineation and definition of subject disciplines is indispensable. Gómez, Bordons, Fernández, and Méndez. (1996) pointed to the lack of unified classification criteria among the different databases as well as to the absence of standardization of subject classifications in those as one of the most crucial problems in obtaining appropriate subject delineation for conducting sound, reliable and reproducible bibliometric and scientometric studies.

Indeed, the fact of organizing and representing the structure of scientific knowledge in an appropriate system of disciplines and subject categories is not only interesting from the viewpoint of research evaluation but from other perspectives as well. Thus, several authors dealing with computerized visualization methods attempted to map the structure of scientific knowledge using information extracted from the large multidisciplinary abstract and citation indexes, above all, Thomson Reuters' Web of Knowledge (Small & Garfield 1985; Bassecoulard & Zitt, 1999; Boyack, Klavans & Börner, 2005; Moya-Anegón et al., 2004; Moya-Anegón et al., 2007; Janssens, Zhang, De Moor & Glänzel, 2009; Leydesdorff & Rafols, 2009; Zhang, Janssens, Liang & Glänzel, 2010) and Elsevier's Scopus (Klavans & Boyack, 2007; Klavans & Boyack, 2009; Leydesdorff, Moya-Anegón & Guerrero-Bote, 2010). These two databases are considered the most prestigious and reliable multidisciplinary bibliographic information sources for the scientific community up to the present. Both databases assign documents through the journals, in which they have been published, using a similar two-level disciplinary classification scheme consisting of subject areas and subject categories.

At this point, it should be remembered that science and research are ever-changing phenomena. New topics are emerging for different intra-scientific, social, economic and further reasons while other topics might gradually diminish and disappear or just change their thematic focus (cf. Glänzel & Thijs, 2012), respectively. An obvious consequence of these processes is that subject classification schemes should mirror and reflect evolution. Due to this necessity to adapt to the shifts of science and research, classification needs to be regularly

updated and improved. This could result in some changes in the structure of the subject classification scheme, for instance, in introducing new categories, removing old and “extinct” ones, or merging or splitting up some of them. Leydesdorff (2002) considered this problem and propose to refresh subject classification schemes by analyzing structural links among journals covered in Science Citation Index, what he called “dynamic and evolutionary updates”.

A vast number of methods and techniques have been developed to categorize and organize information stored in both specialized and multidisciplinary bibliographic databases. Among the different proposals we found solutions based on expert assessment, intellectual, heuristic and pragmatic approaches as well as various statistical and computerized methods and techniques based on social-network analysis, reference analysis, subject filtering, specialized queries, and so on. All these proposals have been applied to different units of analysis, that is, papers, journals or even subject categories themselves and, of course, using different units of measures based on lexical components (keywords or terms extracted from title, abstract, authors’ addresses, or the full text of the document), citation links, or a combination of both.

Related works

The exponential growth of information aforementioned involved simultaneous implications as launching of databases to cope with this flood of information. This was also boosted by the breathtaking development of computer science, information technology and electronic communication, which allowed the rise of digital formats and expedited the diffusion of information around the world. This technological development motivated a considerable number of researchers to start exploring the possibility of automatic classification of information recorded in databases, notably, for information retrieval purposes. For this goal different computerized techniques were used. Among these, clustering was one of the most popular methods. As far back 70s, Cormack (1971) published an exhaustive and helpful bibliography study of subject classification topics focusing on definitions of different similarity measures and the theoretical framework of alternative clustering techniques.

Classification for Information Retrieval Purposes

In information retrieval, automatic classification was mainly used to facilitate retrieval and to improve its efficiency. In the first tests, the set of analyzed items were rather small. However, the advances and development of computer science (increasing CPU power and speed, storage capacity and improving algorithms) allowed to process large data sets. Price and Schiminovich (1968) ventured into automatic classification scheme generation through a clustering experiment based on bibliographic coupling of 240 theoretical documents in high-energy physics. Later on, Schiminovich (1971) published a new study in which an algorithm for the automatic detection of related document clusters based on bibliographic links was determined. He proposed his *bibliographic pattern discovery algorithm*, as a tool for automatic document classification and retrieval, offering good balance of recall and precision. By using a modified release of Schiminovich’s algorithm, Bichteler and Parsons (1974) proposed an automatic classification through citations extracted from a *triggering file* of documents associated via bibliographic information. Croft (1980) developed a clustering method to retrieve relevant

document clusters matching with queries. Queries were thus grouped into different clusters of similar documents using probability estimates. Van Rijsbergen carried out single-link clustering on different samples in order to establish a hierarchical cluster classification to improve efficiency of document retrieval (van Rijsbergen, 1974; van Rijsbergen & Croft, 1975). An interesting and broad review of research literature on clustering approaches used in document retrieval was published by Willett (1988), who basically targeted on hierarchical agglomerative clustering methods.

Bibliometric/Scientometric classification schemes

In bibliometrics/scientometrics the application of citation-based methods in building measures for clustering techniques and classification algorithms was a very common research point in the use of SCI data. Small and Griffith (1974) applied a single-link clustering method using co-citation strength on a set of 1832 SCI highly cited documents to detect and map scientific specialties. Garfield (1975) reported that SCI categories were, in part, “algorithmically identified by the simplest clustering techniques”. He tested clustering on the basis of citation links among SCI documents as to set an automatic classification system that enabled updating and modifying classification scheme periodically (Garfield, Malin & Small, 1974). Small and other scientists tried to cluster SCI database using co-citation links as the underlying measure. In a first study, Small and Sweeney (1985) exposed two method enhancements, namely, *fractional citation counting* to weight citation links according to the number of emitted citations, and *variable level clustering* to define the maximum size of the final clusters to be obtained. In a related second work (Small, Sweeney & Greenlee, 1985) the last methodological improvement, particularly, *iterative clustering of clusters* to map SCI fields in terms of scientific literature covered by this database was introduced. Glenisson, Glänzel, and Persson (2005) prepared a pilot study relying on 19 papers published in a special issue of the journal *Scientometrics*, where they combined text-based and bibliometric methods to test the performance of hierarchical clustering of full-text versus abstract-title-keywords and compared their results with the topic structure created by the guest-editors.

Matrices and networks of journal-level aggregation

Hitherto, we have talked about cluster analysis at the document level. However, tests regarding cluster algorithms and methods on citation measures were developed not only on papers sets and, very early journals have become the object of study in assignment and classification. The reason is that documents can indirectly be assigned to subjects through the scope or classification of journals covered in multidisciplinary databases thus allowing subject delineation at the field and discipline level to prepare accurate bibliometric and scientometric meso- and macro-level studies. Narin (1976) was a pioneer in proposing article classification through the assignment of journals, in which they have been published, to subject categories. Thereby, Carpenter and Narin (1973) performed clustering on cross-citation data from 288 SCI journals in physics, chemistry and molecular biology field looking for a more precise level of journal classification than disciplines. Bassecoulard and Zitt (1999) stated that “journals remain the main substrate for macro-level classifications”, and on this basis, they presented an automatic multi-level classification of scientific journals conducting a hierarchical clustering on

a journal-journal cross-citation matrix. They obtained 141 specialties and 32 sub-disciplines that were mapped and compared with other classifications schemes, namely, the CHI subfields and ISI subject categories showing a large degree of similarity and compatibility with the latter one. Chen (2008) used the *affinity propagation* cluster algorithm on a journal-journal citation links from Thomson Reuters' Journal Citation Reports (JCR) in order to achieve an automatic classification of SCI and SSCI journals. The algorithm was applied to distances among journals by using a cutoff parameter to constrain a maximal distance that permitted to determine different levels of resolution in the final classification schemes. Rafols and Leydesdorff (2009) made a comparative study of two content-based and two algorithmic decomposition of aggregated journal-journal citation matrix based on 7,611 journals from 2006 volume of the JCR. Results evidenced a more homogeneous and overlapped classification from content-based decomposition and a limited matching between similar categories of different classification schemes. However, maps depicted and relied on four classification schemes showed a good fit and correspondence. Janssens et al. (2009) developed a hybrid clustering method based on text and citation analysis of about 8,300 journals covered by Thomson Reuters' Web of Science (WoS) in order to improve WoS journal classifications and to get a comparable classification scheme to compare and validate this versus existing "intellectual" subject classification schemes. Here, Ward's hierarchical clustering was used. Later, Zhang et al. (2010) conducted a journal cross-citation analysis on a similar WoS journal set to improve a journal-based subject classification scheme developed earlier by Glänzel and Schubert (2003). They used a combination of statistical, computerized and bibliometric techniques including Ward's hierarchical method for clustering journals, text-mining to label obtained clusters, and several indicators as journal link strength, journal entropies or PageRank algorithm to determine important leading journals within the clusters.

In the present study, we focus on cluster analysis of Scopus journals included in the Scimago Journal & Country Rank (SJR) platform (Scimago, 2007) using a combination of three citation measures, namely, direct citation, co-citation and bibliographic coupling. We follow the suggestion by Persson (2010) to combine these citation measures in a raw and in a normalized way (Weighted Direct Citation and Normalized Weighted Direct Citation respectively).

Material

We retrieved all data from the SJR database. A set of 18,891 Scopus journals included in the SJR platform and covering a period of two years (2009-2010) were captured. Citations were collected and counted at the level of individual papers published in a two-year period and assigned to the journals in which they appeared. No threshold was set regarding citations and document type. Only cited references from 2000 on were taken into account while journal self-citations were discarded since this type of citations tend to have a strong effect on similarity measures without contributing to the actual classification issue.

Methods

Citation-based measures calculation and integration

In the first step a pair-wise journal list containing direct citation, bibliographic coupling and co-citation journal networks was built. These lists represent journal relationships on the basis of raw values expressing the strength of their relations. The three citation-based measures were calculated at the document level and then aggregated to journals. For co-citation and bibliographic coupling calculation, references co-occurring were counted only once per paper following the binary counting proposed by Rousseau and Zuccala (2004) and avoiding what Vargas-Quesada and Moya-Anegón (2007) named *latent co-citation*. Moreover, fractional counting was applied for three citation measures by considering the total number of links given and received by journals in calculating relation strength. In this way, the power of attraction exerted by certain journals, for instance, with a high quantity of citations or pertaining to research fields with a considerable influence could be offset.

Then, we integrated the three lists of journals covering fractionalized direct citation, co-citation and bibliographic coupling in a new one according to Persson's approach to identify research themes through this new combined measure which he named *normalized weighted direct citation (NWDC)* links (Persson, 2010). However, we limited the final list to those journal pairs for which all the three citation-based measures were present. In this way, we took into consideration the Persson's idea of those citation links that are not sharing references and are not being cited together might be out of topic. Hence, the integration of the normalized direct citation, co-citation and bibliographic coupling lists was executed following the next rule:

If $x > 0$ AND $y > 0$ AND $z > 0$ Then $R = x + y + z$

But

If $x = 0$ OR $y = 0$ OR $z = 0$ Then $R = 0$

Where x = direct citation, y = co-citation, z = bibliographic coupling and R = result.

Consequently, the three normalized measures were combined by summing up the values on the condition of all of them are non-zero. After that, the network list consisted of 16,258 citing and 15,266 cited journals.

Clustering performance

The resulting asymmetrical journal-journal list was finally converted into a journal-journal symmetrical matrix by applying cosine similarity on the cited side of the matrix. Due to the large citation network, which includes several thousand journals from different science fields characterized by different citation behaviors, we found an extremely sparse matrix with only 1.81% non-zero values. Cosine let us to make the matrix symmetrical and set similarities among journal vectors at once. Nevertheless, similarities were then transformed into distances according to the $1 - \text{cosine}$ formula and Ward's hierarchical clustering was conducted at last. All these steps were executed in "R" statistical software with the 'lsa' package (Wild, 2011) for Latent Semantic Analysis aimed at calculating cosine similarities.

We executed several tests based on Ward's hierarchical agglomerative clustering in order to determine the best solution adapting to our main goal: to refine journal assignment and improve the SJR journal classification system. Solutions giving 200 to 250 clusters were analyzed and, finally, by considering the number of joined clusters over the different partitions generated from down to top in the dendrogram we found that the solution providing 232 clusters was a good and tailored choice to our final classification objective. This point was reinforced by the fact that the higher the number of clusters generated in each solution, the higher the number of small clusters with a poorer relatedness among the journals comprised.

Labelling clusters

The definitive number of clusters given was labeled by adopting tags from the set of original SJR categories. By doing so, we would facilitate one of the most prevalent problems in clustering analysis such as cluster labeling. Thus, for each cluster we calculated the number of links from journals to former SJR categories and, subsequently, we transformed frequencies into *tf-idf* scores by an adaptation of Salton and Buckley (1988) formula:

$$w_{i,j} = \text{catf}_{i,j} \times \text{Log} (N / \text{cluf}_i)$$

Where $w_{i,j}$ = total weighted score; $\text{catf}_{i,j}$ = raw frequency of category 'i' into cluster 'j'; N = total number of clusters; and cluf_i = number of clusters containing category 'i'

At the same time, we converted the number of links into percentages. Finally, we ranked journals according to *tf-idf* scores and selected those category tags amounting at least 33% of the links which would be designed to delineate the subject of clusters accurately. During the labeling process SJR '*Miscellaneous*' and '*Multidisciplinary*' category tags were discarded. However, using this approach we found some clusters thematically delimited by just the same tags. In these cases, we re-labeled these clusters using significant words extracted from journal titles. Through this combined approach we were keeping core, well-defined and representative categories from the original SJR classification system according to the citation links and detecting emerging categories through the alternative text component at once. In closing, it is worthy to remark that journal multiple assignments were a consequence of cluster labeling process rather than Ward's clustering method, which is hard clustering methods that performs assigning only one journal per cluster.

Assessment of the new classification

In a last phase, we proceeded to assess the performance of the new SJR journal classification by contrasting it with the original SJR classification system. To do so, we prepared a series of indicators applicable to both classification systems including: (1) *number of categories*, (2) *mean number of journals per category*, (3) *mean number of categories per journal*, (4) *overlapping percentage*, (5) *journals changing their classification*, (6) *journals adding categories* and (7) *journals losing categories*. Apart from these indicators we examined the (8) *distributions of journals over categories* given in both systems in order to display some points

such as the distribution curve or the aggregation of journals in some particular categories. To make a reliable and reasonable comparison, only the set of journals included in both classification systems were taken for indicators (5), (6) and (7).

Results

Firstly, we examined the various partitions generated providing 200-250 clusters and could observe that everyone had a common factor: the appearance of two especially large clusters covering journals of the areas of 'Social Sciences & Humanities' (cluster #2) and 'Medicine' (cluster #12). Generally, Ward's method is featured by this phenomenon and one or various large clusters can appear when is executed. Everitt, Landau, Leese, and Stahl (2011) stated that "In standard agglomerative or polythetic divisive clustering, partitions are achieved by selecting one of the solutions in the nested sequence of clusterings that comprise the hierarchy, equivalent to cutting a dendrogram at a particular height (sometimes termed the best cut)". Based on their idea that "Large changes in fusion levels are taken to indicate the best cut" we analyzed the down-top fusions of clusters occurred during the clustering performance, and found that the partition supplying 232, which coincide with the lowest number of joined clusters from the whole set, were appropriate and fitted to our classification goal. Moreover, this argument is underpinned by the fact that the higher the number of clusters generated, the wider the set of small-size clusters obtained resulting less thematically consistent and delineated.

The overall hierarchical structure derived from Ward's clustering method is represented through the dendrogram in figure 1. Due to space constrains and aimed at making clearer and easier its analysis and visualization, we cut the dendrogram at the height of 50 in order to keep only its topside. In this manner we got a simplified version of the hierarchical structure where four core subject areas of Scopus database (Elsevier, 2014), i.e. 'Health Sciences', 'Life Sciences', 'Physical Sciences' and 'Social Sciences' have been identified. In addition, some smaller journal aggregations corresponding to subject categories included in these four large areas are displayed in other branches of the dendrogram. In any case, there seems to be a good deal of coherence among adjacent branches which, at the same time, are in some consonance with Scopus classification at this high level of aggregation. Thus, the dendrogram shows two principal branches. The first one on the left side is an isolated branch covering the area of 'Computer Sciences and Information Systems'. The second principal branch on the right side is much more extensive and comprises of various hierarchical levels. A first main subdivision of this branch is dealing with *Biomedical Sciences*. Thus, from left to right, we can find a branch referring to 'Cellular and Molecular Biology' together with two other branches on 'Medical Research' and 'Health Sciences'. On its side, the second main subdivision on the right side presents seven branches. The first and second branches respectively cover a specific aggregation of journals on 'Optics' as a component of a subsequent higher aggregation of journals on 'Physical Sciences'. Similarly, the third and fourth branches include journals on 'Zoology' as a fraction of a higher group of journals on 'Life Sciences'. The fifth branch shows a separated group of journals on 'Mathematics' which is just followed by two new branches consisting of journals on 'Engineering' and, finally, a wide set of journals from 'Social Sciences and Humanities' areas.

Figure 1: Dendrogram of Ward's SJR journal clustering

As aforesaid, the two large clusters on 'Social Sciences & Humanities' and 'Medicine' are present throughout the distinct solutions generated by the method. In spite of being a frequent issue in Ward's method performance, this fact is not satisfactory to our classification objective since, similarly to relatively small clusters, high-size clusters do not constitute well-defined and delimited subject groups of journals. Besides, the distribution of journals over the 232 subject clusters categories produced a great aggregation of journals in only two categories producing a far skewed distribution. To solve this shortcoming we decided to repeat the full methodological procedure on the sub-matrices referring to clusters #2 and #12 of our 232-cluster solution. For both clusters this implied (1) to extract raw data of the three citation-based measure networks for each journal included only in these clusters, (2) to calculate fractional counting, (3) to combine the measures following the rule which binds to the three citation-based measures to appear together in the matrix, (4) to apply cosine similarity on cited side of the matrix, (5) to execute Ward's clustering method, (6) to determine a good solution by analyzing large changes in fusion levels to set the best-cut and, finally, (7) to label the clusters.

After executing the whole process, cluster #2 originally formed by 1788 journals was then reduced to 804 which were spread over 35 new clusters. On its side, from the initial 951 journals in cluster #12 only 385 left spread over a set of 25 clusters. In summarizing, the initial network of 18,891 SJR journals was pruned to a final number of 13,716 journals after

performing the second phase of our methodological procedure while the final number of subject clusters raised to 290 resulting from the 232 original clusters of the first clustering phase minus the clusters #2 and #12 then divided into 35 and 25 respectively. The new final classification originated as a consequence of our method is accessible at the following link: <http://www.ugr.es/~benjamin/new-sjr-classification.pdf>

Table 1 presents some relevant indicators comparing the original SJR classification to the new SJR classification system generated.

	ORIGINAL SJR CLASSIFICATION	NEW SJR CLASSIFICATION
Number of classified journals	18,891	13,716
Number of categories	308	298
Mean number of journals per category	61.33	46.03
Mean number of categories per journal	1.61	1.42
Overlapping percentage	60.73	42.26

Table 1: Some relevant indicators about the original and new SJR classification systems

The first indicator refers to the set of journals included in each system. Original SJR covers a total of 18,891 journals that were then decreased to 13,716 in the new system because of the combination of citation-based measures used in the 2-phase clustering applied. A more interesting data is related to the final set of active categories in both systems, the original SJR has 308 categories while the new cluster derived system amounts a total of 298 categories. However, a relevant issue derived from the comparison is that only 159 categories are being shared by both systems. Therefore, a total of 139 (Annex I) have been generated as a consequence of the method applied, especially, by the labeling process executed. It is important to clarify that the number of clusters derived from our method (290) does not agree with the number of categories specified in table 1 (298) due to the multiple assignment of category tags occurred in some clusters. For instance, cluster #148 was labeled as ‘Cardiology and Cardiovascular Medicine’ + ‘Internal Medicine’ category tags, while cluster #210 was assigned to ‘Cardiology and Cardiovascular Medicine’ and #175 ‘Endocrinology’ + ‘Cardiology and Cardiovascular Medicine’ categories. The several possible combinations and the distinct number of category tags assigned to the set of clusters is, therefore, the only reason behind the difference in the number of categories included in table 1 and the number of clusters given by Ward’s clustering method.

Admittedly the set of journals of original SJR overcomes in more than 5,000 journals to the new one by contrast the number of categories in both original and new SJR systems are quite similar, amounting 308 and 298 respectively. This fact could explain the much better results of new classification system regarding the indicator on ‘Mean number of journals per category’, and, to a lesser extent, on indicators on ‘Mean number of categories per journal’ and ‘Overlapping percentage’. However, this subset of over 5,000 journals is characterized by having a scant influence in the whole journal network of combined citation-based measures and very low interaction among them. Therefore, the better outcomes of new SJR classification system seem not merely a consequence of the reduction of the number of journals but rather

the good results derived from the methodology proposed. This argument can be contrasted by comparing the results of the above mentioned indicators only on the 13,716 journals matching in both classification systems (table 2).

	SJR CLASSIFICATION REDUCED VERSION (13,716 JOURNALS)	NEW SJR CLASSIFICATION
Number of classified journals	13,716	13,716
Number of categories	297	298
Mean number of journals per category	46.18	46.03
Mean number of categories per journal	1.62	1.42
Overlapping percentage	62.18	42.26

Table 2: Some relevant indicators about the 13,716 journals matching in the original and new SJR classification systems

The '*Mean number of categories per journal*' and '*Overlapping percentage*' are complementary indicators which differs only in the way to express their values, i.e. as decimal and percentages. The overlapping percentage was calculated using the next formula:

$$B - A / A * 100$$

Where A = journals covered by the system (or in other words, the set of journals under consideration); and B = journal multi-assignment (set of classified journals including multi-assigned journals, that is, assigned to more than one category).

A very significant issue not covered in tables 1 and 2 is in connection with the number of journals suffering changes in their original classification. From the full set of 13,716 journals under study, a total of 1,988 altered their classification by changing one or several of their assigned categories. Apart from these changes, many other journals suffered either increases or decreases in the number of categories they covered. Thus, 2,426 journals adding at least one category in the new SJR classification system while a number of 3,951 lost categories with respect to the original SJR classification. This means that taking into account the journals changing their original classification and the journals adding/losing categories the percentage of SJR journals modifying their category assignment from the original to the new system amounts 60.99% which is a really high figure.

Linking with changes in the category assignment of journals and the overlapping indicators of table 1, the figure 2 represents the multi-assignment of journals in the original SJR system and new SJR one. In this point, also the new SJR system returned better results, by decreasing the number of multi-assigned journals. Thus, in the new SJR system, over 72% of journals were assigned to only 1 category, almost 19% to 2 categories, a little bit more of 5% to 3 categories, and approximately the same percentage (around 2%) of journals allocated to 4 and 5 categories. There are not journals with more than 5 categories in this system. On its side, the reduced SJR system amounted 63.7% of journals in one category, 20.6% of journals were assigned to 2 categories, 9.9% to 3 categories, almost 4% to 4 categories whereas over 1.2%

were allocated to 5 categories. In contrast to the new system, here a residual quantity of journals (around 0.7%) was ascribed to more than 5 categories.

Figure 2: Journal multi-assignment in the original and new SJR classification systems

Another important issue to be analyzed is the distribution of journals over the 298 categories obtained from the new journal classification. Figure 3 shows the distributions of the original and new SJR systems. A simple glance is enough to uncover a much more balanced and softer distribution of journals over categories in the latter. The original system, basically, revealed a high skew in the first part of the distribution where 'Medicine (miscellaneous)' category appears amounting 5.2% of the total set of journals classified. However, although the initial part of the distribution is too flatter for the new classification system, approximately on the middle point of the distribution both systems holds quite similar and parallel.

Figure 3: Distribution of journals over categories in the original and new SJR classification systems

Figure 3 is supplemented by the table 3, which reflects the top-20 categories in the ranking of the distribution of journals over categories in both systems. By observing the number of journals per category in each system it can be seen that as a general rule, the original SJR classification offers higher concentrations of journals per category than the new classification system. According to figure 3, this concentration is extremely notable in the first category of the reduced SJR classification where 'Medicine (miscellaneous)' amount 1579 journals whereas in the new one only 381 journals were included by the category 'Social Studies'. Despite the high number of new categories given by the new SJR classification system, a total of 4 categories are shared in the top-20 table, namely, 'Electrical and Electronic Engineering', 'Sociology and Political Science', 'Public Health, Environmental and Occupational Health' and 'Psychiatry and Mental Health'. This point indicates certain coherence and concordance between both classifications systems even more when the set of 'Miscellaneous' categories are not being used in the new classification system.

REDUCED ORIGINAL SJR CLASSIFICATION SYSTEM				NEW SJR CLASSIFICATION SYSTEM			
Category	Num. of Journals	%	Cum. %	Category	Num. of Journals	%	Cum. %
Medicine (miscellaneous)	1579	5.20	5.20	Social Studies	381	1.95	1.95
Education	524	1.73	6.93	Electrical and Electronic Engineering	349	1.79	3.74
Sociology and Political Science	460	1.52	8.44	Computer & Information Systems Engineering	342	1.75	5.49
Geography, Planning and Development	450	1.48	9.92	Mechanical Engineering	328	1.68	7.17
History	444	1.46	11.39	Immunology	289	1.48	8.66
Electrical and Electronic Engineering	406	1.34	12.72	Cancer Research	285	1.46	10.12
Cultural Studies	375	1.24	13.96	Oncology	281	1.44	11.56
Social Sciences (miscellaneous)	374	1.23	15.19	Neurology (clinical)	257	1.32	12.87
Economics and Econometrics	368	1.21	16.40	Cell Biology	251	1.29	14.16
Literature and Literary Theory	366	1.21	17.61	Orthopedics and Sports Medicine	237	1.21	15.37
Engineering (miscellaneous)	356	1.17	18.78	Computer Systems	230	1.18	16.55
Psychology (miscellaneous)	351	1.16	19.94	Sociology and Political Science	221	1.13	17.69
Public Health, Environmental and Occupational Health	335	1.10	21.04	Psychiatry and Mental Health	220	1.13	18.81
Plant Science	327	1.08	22.12	Development Studies	219	1.12	19.94
Language and Linguistics	327	1.08	23.19	Public Health, Environmental and Occupational Health	215	1.10	21.04
Psychiatry and Mental Health	325	1.07	24.26	Strategy and Management	198	1.01	22.05
Animal Science and Zoology	315	1.04	25.30	Applied Mathematics	185	0.95	23.00
Mathematics (miscellaneous)	306	1.01	26.31	Molecular Medicine	180	0.92	23.92
Cardiology and Cardiovascular Medicine	273	0.90	27.21	Biochemistry	179	0.92	24.84
Agricultural and Biological Sciences (miscellaneous)	269	0.89	28.09	Genetics	173	0.89	25.73

Table3: Ranking of the top-20 categories in the original and new SJR classification systems

Up to now we have contrasted the results of the new SJR classification with the original SJR classification system in order to reveal the improvements obtained through our proposal. Nevertheless, it might also be interesting to compare the results generated by this methodology with those coming from a previous work based on a different combination of citation measures and distinct clustering methods, namely, Louvain and VOS community detection algorithms (Gómez-Núñez, Batagelj, Vargas-Quesada, Moya-Anegón & Chinchilla-Rodríguez, 2014). To this end, we have introduced the table 4 collecting the same indicators

exposed in tables 1 and 2. Furthermore, indicators referring to journals changing, adding or losing categories in relation to the original SJR classification have also been added.

	NEW SJR CLASSIFICATION	LOUVAIN 18	VOS 15
Number of classified journals	13716	17287	17729
Number of categories	298	272	267
Mean number of journals per category	46.03	63.56	66.40
Mean number of categories per journal	1.42	1.48	1.50
Overlapping percentage	42.26	47.58	49.89
Journals changing their classification	1988 (14.49%)	5784 (33.46%)	5874 (33.13%)
Journals adding categories	2426 (17.69%)	3820 (22.10%)	4192 (23.64%)
Journals losing categories	3951 (28.81%)	4540 (26.26%)	4603 (25.96%)

Table 4: Some relevant indicators about the new SJR classification based on Ward's clustering and hard combination of citation measures and previous classifications developed by Louvain and VOS community detection and soft combination of citation measures.

Several important points may be remarked from the indicators shown in table 4. First of all, we can notice that classification based on Louvain and VOS provided larger sets of classified journals. However, this was not a result of algorithm performance, which in all cases allow clustering the whole set of journals, but rather a consequence of the harder combination of the citation measures used in the present work (citation AND co-citation AND coupling) in comparison to the former one (citation OR co-citation OR coupling) and other methodological procedures. Furthermore, the 2-phase clustering conducted in this work favored the creation of a higher number of new categories with respect to Louvain and VOS methods, overcoming them in 26 and 31 categories respectively. Obviously, a smaller set of journals in tandem with a higher set of categories will give rise to a lower 'mean number of journals per category' in the new SJR classification system. On its side, indicators concerning the 'Mean number of categories per journal' and 'Overlapping percentage' which are less influenced by the size of the journal and category sets revealed the best results for new SJR classification system, followed not far by Louvain and VOS system.

More significant findings can be extracted by analyzing the figures on journals changing, adding or losing categories in the three systems under comparison, especially when figures are transformed into percentages. It should be emphasized that while the new SJR classification presents the lowest values in journals changing and adding categories by far, conversely, it has the highest value in relation to journals losing categories. This fact uncovers a general refinement of classification through a decrease of overlapping in journal classification which is validated and corroborated by the data supplied by the earlier indicators on 'Mean number of categories per journal' and 'Overlapping percentage'.

Discussion and conclusions

In a previous study (Gómez-Núñez et al., 2014) we used the Person's citation-based measure combination (Weighted Direct Citation) to cluster journals of SJR in order to improve their classification regardless only one or several measures were present at the same time during their integration. In contrast to it, we have now used an alternative hard combination of normalized citation-based measures (Normalized Weighted Direct Citation) where only couples of journal of the network meeting values for direct citation, co-citation and coupling links at once were contemplated. This novel proposal has emerged as a solid method to refine and update SJR journal classification system by several reasons, namely:

1. Persson (2010) applied the combination of citation-based measures with the aim of detecting research themes within LIS field. Here, we have adopted his approach as a reliable proposal to (a) update the classification systems of SJR platform and to (b) refine the journal adscription to the SJR categories. A total of 139 new categories representing fitted and emerging topics like 'Social Work', 'Nanoscience and Nanotechnology' or 'Plastic Surgery' among others, have been introduced into the SJR classification system. Regarding the refinement of journal assignment our method provoked that more than 8000 journals suffered changes in their classification by either altering their adscription or by losing/adding categories.
2. In relation to the latter point, the reduction of (a) journal multi-assignment together with an (b) overall lower concentration of journals over categories suggests an improvement in the journal classification in spite of having a smaller set of journals in the new system. The representation of the journal distribution showed a marked enhancement in the new system obtained with a flatter and less skewed final distribution of journals.
3. In our view, the combination of the three citation-based measures helps to maximize the cluster effect, even more when the hard combination proposed here is applied. We based this argument on the obviousness of the higher the number of variables to compare between two items, the richer the likelihood to identify similarities or dissimilarities between them by widening the possibilities of the comparison.
4. Apart from the advances aforementioned, our method allowed to replace very general categories as 'Miscellaneous' characterized by covering a broad scope and an big concentrations of journals in favor of new categories discovered as a consequence of our method performance, specially by means of the labeling stage.

Although our proposal has reported reliable and solid findings in updating and improving the SJR classification system by offering a fine-tuning in the assignment of journals to categories, a lower overlapping and a refinement and reduction of the number of categories in use, we have also found two main shortcomings in its performance concerning the following points:

1. Over 5000 journals from the initial network of SJR journals were isolated from the study because they did not satisfy the condition of having direct citation, co-citation and coupling together during the hard combination followed by our method. However, this fact should not be considered as fail of the method rather a requirement to enrich the comparison and extend the difference among the journal clusters obtained. Moreover,

some other method, such as reference analysis or sibling journals should be proposed in order to classify the journals left. Earlier we have already used the analysis of references to improve SJR classification with optimal results (Gómez-Núñez, Vargas-Quesada, Moya-Anegón & Glänzel, 2011). Therefore, these all journals excluded by this method could be integrated in the set of clusters or subject categories generated now.

2. Then, two huge clusters have emerged from Ward's method over the different partitions analyzed. Indeed, this is a very usual issue in Ward's hierarchical agglomerative clustering performance. In addition, He (1999) noticed that this phenomenon was also favored when sparse matrices are being used, such as in the case of the citation matrix coming from citation patterns among SJR journals, with over 98% of zero values. To solve this question we have opted for using a pragmatic approach based on achieving our main purpose of refining and updating SJR journal classification. Thus, we have implemented a second round of clustering on two huge clusters detected which allowed refining the assignment of journals included in them. At the same time, the second round of clustering produced a complementary classification with new specific categories which enriched and improved the previous set of categories derived from single clustering procedure.

In relation to incoming and future research works, it seems to be interesting to address other journal classification procedures from different approaches. Network analysis arises as a quite feasible choice. Also, it would be interesting to enhance the methodology described here by combining citation-links with text-based methods. To conclude with avenues of future research, we would like to make a final reflection in looking for a reliable and consistent technique to assess the goodness-of-classification of the cluster-based solution provided by our method. Finally, it would be meaningful to focus on the classification dilemmas concerning multidisciplinary scientific journals.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our appreciation to Diego Guzmán Morales for supporting in preparing data set as well as easing to solve computational problems and providing orientation in technical questions. Also, we want to thank to Wolfgang Glänzel and Bart Thijs for their patient and inestimable help.

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Annex I: New SJR categories emerging from our classification proposal based on Ward's hierarchical agglomerative

CATEGORY	
1	Aerospace Science, Technology & Engineering
2	Agribusiness
3	Agricultural Engineering
4	Agricultural Science
5	Alcohol & Drug Abuse
6	American History
7	Applied Physics
8	Aquaculture
9	Behavioural Sciences
10	Bioethics
11	Biomedical Research
12	Business Ethics
13	Cardiothoracic surgery
14	Ceramic materials
15	Chemical Engineering
16	Chemical Science & Technology
17	Child & Developmental Psychology
18	Chinese Medicine
19	Classical Studies
20	Combinatorics
21	Composites
22	Computer & Information Systems Engineering
23	Computer Systems
24	Contemporary European History
25	Criminology & Criminal Justice
26	Deafness
27	Dentistry
28	Development Studies
29	Developmental Disabilities Research
30	Earth Sciences
31	Economic History
32	Economics
33	Educational Research
34	Electromagnetics & Microwave
35	Electronics
36	Energy & Environmental Policy
37	Engineering Geology
38	Engineering Science & Technology
39	Environmental Chemical Engineering
40	Environmental economics

41	Environmental Pollution
42	Evidence-Based Medicine
43	Evolutionary Biology
44	Family Counseling & Psychology
45	Forensic Psychology
46	Forensic Science & Legal Medicine
47	Geophysics and Planetary Research
48	Geotechnical Engineering
49	Health Administration
50	Health Communication
51	Health Psychology
52	Healthcare
53	Higher Education
54	History of France
55	History of Science
56	Human Biology
57	Imaging
58	Infection Control
59	Infectious Diseases and Clinical Microbiology
60	International Law
61	Language
62	Learning & Educational Technology
63	Linguistics & Language
64	Literary Studies
65	Literature
66	Macroeconomics & Finance
67	Management Engineering
68	Materials Engineering
69	Mathematical Analysis
70	Mathematical Biology
71	Mathematics (general)
72	Mathematics Education
73	Medical Societies
74	Medical Ultrasound
75	Medicine, General
76	Medicine, General (Ibero-America)
77	Medicine, General (India)
78	Medicine, General (Iran)
79	Medicine, General (Middle East)
80	Medicine, General (Poland)
81	Music Education
82	Mycology
83	Nanomaterials
84	Nanoscience and Nanotechnology
85	Neuropsychology & Cognitive Neuroscience

86	Neuroscience & Brain Research
87	Neurosurgery
88	Nuclear & High Energy Physics
89	Nuclear & Pharmaceutical Chemistry
90	Nuclear Medicine
91	Numerical Methods
92	Nursing (general)
93	Nutrition
94	Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
95	Paleoecology (quaternary)
96	Pathology
97	Pediatric Primary Care
98	Pediatrics, Women and Child Health
99	Petroleum Engineering
100	Philosophy of Psychology
101	Physics
102	Phytopathology
103	Plant & Agricultural Research
104	Plant Biotechnology
105	Plasma Physics
106	Plastic Surgery
107	Politics
108	Power Electronics
109	Proteomics
110	Psychology
111	Psychopedagogy
112	Psychotherapy
113	Public Health
114	Radiology & Imaging
115	Risk Management
116	Science, Technology and Society
117	Sismology
118	Sleep Medicine
119	Social & Economic History
120	Social & Political Philosophy
121	Social Economics
122	Social Policy
123	Social Studies
124	Social Work
125	Sociology
126	Sport Psychology
127	Sports & Leisure
128	Terramechanics
129	Textile Technology
130	Therapeutics

131	Traumatology
132	Tribology
133	Vascular Surgery
134	Veterinary
135	Veterinary Research and Animal Science
136	Waste Technology & Management
137	Water Resource Management
138	Wildlife Biology
139	Wounds